

A Fully Integrated Coherent Transmitter for High Throughput Downlink Scenarios

Peter Forde¹, Javier Díaz Otero Francisco¹ and Álvarez García David¹

¹School of Telecommunications Engineering, University of Vigo, As Lagoas, Marcosende, Vigo, 36310, Galicia, Spain.

Contributing authors: p.forde4@gmail.com; fjdiaz@com.uvigo.es; velocier@gmail.com;

Abstract

There is a growing demand for compact, high throughput optical satellite communications terminals, due to ever-increasing usage of CubeSats and NanoSats with tight volume and mass constraints, as well as increasing demands on the radio frequency spectrum as a communications channel. In this work, a fully integrated photonic coherent transmitter has been designed and simulated, with the intent of providing a solution to this technology gap. The chip is capable of establishing a 2 Gb/s link up to 600 km range with a proposed portable ground station.

Keywords: Photonics, Satellite, Downlink, Indium Phosphide

1 Introduction

In the space sector, Nanosats and CubeSats in particular are being utilised for an ever-greater fraction of both scientific and commercial space missions. CubeSats are composed of multiple 10cm cubic modules that are restricted to 1.33kg mass per module. The increasing number of satellites in LEO (Low-Earth Orbit), driven in part by the growth of the small sat industry, has led to RF (Radio Frequency) bands becoming crowded, and it can be challenging to acquire licenses (Clements 2016). One solution to this is to utilise optical communications, it is possible a PIC (Photonic Integrated Circuit) could be a part of that solution. There is also a growing demand for compact, high throughput

optical satellite communications terminals, due to the aforementioned ever-increasing usage of CubeSats and NanoSats. This is due to the tight volume and mass constraints for these platforms. Coupling this with the increasing demands on the RF spectrum as a communications channel, it becomes clear that a compact, OpCom solution is needed. In this work, a fully integrated InP photonic coherent transmitter has been designed and simulated, with the intent of providing a solution to this technology gap. Additionally, since CubeSats can now be equipped with more advanced payloads which can generate large volumes of data (Tsitras and Kingston 2010). This further highlights the need for low power, high data rate links.

2 Link Budget Calculations

The initial step to establish the viability of the proposed transmitter device, was to take an estimate of a photonic integrated circuits (PIC) output power and use this as the basis for link budget calculations. Additionally, Reising (2017) demonstrated a commercial off the shelf (COTS) ground station for OpCom utilising a Celestron CPC 1100, with an aperture diameter of 27.9 cm. This was used as an example of a reasonably achievable ground station with which to test the capabilities of the transmitter against, and its characteristics were used in the receiver component of the link budget calculations.

Calculations from Gibalina (2017) were used to write a python programme to display the Necessary transmitter power against receiver diameter, for both PIN and avalanche photodiode (APD) detectors, in order to see at which data rate, range, power output of the transmitter, receiving a signal was possible. The calculations assume a relatively cloudless day, but transmission spectra for the chosen wavelength (1.55 micron) indicate that water vapour content and atmospheric density have little effect on the transmission of the signal. (Figure 1).

Fig. 1 Transmission Spectra for 1.4-1.9 microns, with varied atmospheric weighting (Chiboucas 2022)

Figure (2) was the result of multiple adjustments to various variables. It includes gain attributed to including an EDFA from iXblue, which provides a gain of 30dB and is graded for space missions. With that included, a chip with an 8mW output can deliver 2gbps from 600km range to a groundstation with a

25cm diameter or larger, which fits for the suggested groundstation mentioned earlier. This assumed beam divergence can be confined to 0.2mrad, which is possible with multiple COTS beam collimators for fibre optics.

Fig. 2 Link Budget Results

Considering that the target mission for the transmitter is an LEO CubeSat mission, a 400km orbit is most likely. Therefore, if we take into consideration the 600km link distance we have calculated for, this will enable the link to be established from an elevation angle as little as 55 degrees. In the following chart (figure 3) the orbital altitude h for our case is 400 km, while the slant range p is 600 km.

Fig. 3 Diagram illustrating the relationship between elevation angle, slant range, and orbital altitude. (Saeed 2020)

With all these considerations and effects in mind, we want to design an integrated chip consisting of a coherent transmitter that can form a link with a ground station in these conditions. For this task we consider using InP platform as it has active and passive elements. The HHI platform was selected due to time to fabrication, performance of the DFB laser and the availability of spot size converters (SSC) for ease of alignment with external optics.

3 Test Chip and Transmitter Chip Designs

3.1 Coherent Transmitter Designs

To begin, with all the considerations of the previous chapter, the system block diagram decided upon was that of figure (4). In reality there was more interplay between the designs and building blocks used, and the link budget calculations, but this was the general decided upon layout. With that decided the next task was to design the test chips for individual components on the transmitter chip.

Fig. 4 Transmitter Block Diagram

3.2 Test Chip Designs

To reiterate, the test chip's purpose is to allow for characterisation of the building blocks after they have been exposed to a radiation dose to simulate the effects of this aspect of the space environment on their functionality. To this end a test chip was designed to allow for each building block; distributed feedback (DFB) laser, Modulator (Mach Zender), semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA), Photodiode, to be tested individually. As a starting point the following block diagram was created:

This design would allow for each component to be measured individually, has a central loop between two SSCs for assisting in alignment of the chip, and has a full transmitter circuit so potentially a measurement could be done of

splitter with an 80:20 splitting ratio was included. The lower powered end of the split was sent to a photodiode. The intention of this was to enable on-sat diagnostics of the transmitter system, allowing for the components operation to be managed by the on-board computer rather than relying on diagnostics from the ground station. Potentially, this could allow for different modulation formats to be chosen based on link conditions. This could increase the efficiency of transmissions, as if the link is strained a lower data rate, better signal-noise ration (SNR) data modulation format like on-off keying (OOK) could be used, while quadrature phase key shifting (QPSK) is switched to when conditions allow. Additionally, the satellite can understand if there is a fault occurring with, for example, the DFB laser, and switch to a redundant laser on chip. A future chip could be designed to take advantage of this, which has a second transmitter circuit on the same chip, without the test structures, each transmitter system therefore having a full back up built in.

With these considerations in mind the following block diagram for the circuit was drawn up, and used as a guide for the circuit layout:

Fig. 6 Finalised Transmitter Chip Block Diagram

3.3.1 Chip Packaging

For the assembly of this chip, the 12 DC and 8 RF connections were wire bonded to a high-speed electrical carrier, and the optical fibre pig tailing of the

10 optical ports were performed by VLC. The electrical carrier was designed on a ceramic substrate for high frequency signals, allowing up to 20GHz operation for the RF ports controlling the EAM and therefore the signal modulation. For thermal control a bond-pad for a thermistor was placed close to the PIC, peltier-cell and thermistor will be connected to spare pin-connectors on the PCB. Fujikura PM1550 fibre optic cables were chosen for the fibre array. They are single mode fibres with larger than -20dB crosstalk. The PCB provides the mechanical support on top of which to die-attach face-up the PIC using a thermal conductive epoxy. This solution enhances the mechanical robustness of the optical fibres, and it can allow to use an embedded Peltier cell for temperature stabilization.

Fig. 7 Illustration of the PIC Assembly

4 Simulation Results and Discussion

Some data from simulations of the transmitter chip in Lumerical Interconnect will be presented and discussed below.

Fig. 8 Diagram illustrating the measurement points used for producing the following graphs in Lumerical Interconnect

The EAM is being powered by a PBRs driven applied voltage switching between -4 and 0 Volts. At this setting the EAM is able to absorb all the light when fully powered, creating sharp square waveforms for encoding the signal. The only noticeable difference at location 3 being from propagation

loss, insertion loss and the 80:20 split the splitter performs as mentioned in the design description. The SOA was driven by the same PBRS as the EAM, as if left in its on state it pumped low noise levels in the system too much for the 0 and 1 bits to be distinguishable.

Fig. 9 Summary of the previous charts for ease of viewing how the power changes throughout the chip.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In summary, a PIC has been designed and simulated for facilitating LEO Small Sat downlinks, capable of approximately 2 Gb/s data rate. The simulations are promising. When the transmitter and test PICs are fabricated they will be tested under LEO radiation conditions to test their rad-hardness. A plan for packaging the transmitter for testing is also in place, and future work will integrate it with an EDFA, and test the transmitter in free space on an optical bench in order to verify the beam is constrained enough for the link budget to be considered accurate.

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